

Impact of BT Technology on Cotton Productivity in India

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Abstract

Since the introduction of BT cotton in India there has been a serious debate going on its impact on cost, returns and productivity. Andhra Pradesh continue to be the largest cultivator of BT cotton in India and it occupies third position among Indian cotton growing states both in terms of area as well as outturn. In this context, it would be appropriate to analyze the output and efficiency of inputs used in cotton cultivation in Andhra Pradesh state of India.. The Cobb-Douglas production and decomposition analysis techniques were used to estimate the influence of factors and BT technology on output change. The results of the estimated production functions reveal that seeds and fertilizer is the most important input to which output is highly responsive in both BT and Non-BT cotton crop situations. The output elasticity of pesticide is higher in Non-BT cotton cultivation than that of in BT cotton cultivation. The decomposition revealed that the net impact of BT technology alone is estimated to have increased the output by 10.88 per cent. It is necessary to motivate the farmers for cultivation of BT cotton with appropriate extension strategies and policy measures.

Keywords: BT technology, Resource use efficiency, Decomposition of output change, Production function, BT cotton, Non BT cotton.

Introduction

India with its 13 per cent share of world's cotton production ranks the third largest producer of cotton in the world (CABI, 2008). Although India has the world's largest average of cotton, its productivity is among the lowest in the world (F.A.O, 2008). One of the main factors showing impact on the productivity is the fact that the cost on pesticides accounts for major portion of total cost of cultivation. Cotton is highly

susceptible to insects which impacts cotton production. Nearly fifty per cent of the pesticides consumed in India is used only for cotton crop. The chemical control to eliminate these pests have developed high level resistance for the most of chemicals used to control the pest. Such a high level of resistance requires repeated application of pesticides leading to expenditure and crop failures (Jagmail Singh et al, 2007). Andhra Pradesh continue to be the largest cultivator of BT cotton in India and it occupies third position among Indian cotton growing states both in terms of area as well as outturn. The area under cotton in the state accounts for 10.63 per cent of total area and 12.86 per cent of total production in the country. Nearly 85 per cent of total area under cotton cultivation in the state is under BT cotton (ISAAA, 2007). Thus cotton farmers in the state provide livelihood and wage employment to about one tenth of rural population. The living standards of rural people will be effected by the performance of cotton cultivation, which is matter of serious concern (Mahendra Dev S., et al, 2007). With this back drop, the present study is proposed to assess the effect of BT cotton technology on output and efficiency of inputs used in cotton cultivation in Andhra Pradesh state of India during 2007-08.

An attempt is made in this paper to asses the impact of BT cotton technology on cotton output empirically. The objectives of the study are: (i) To assess the resource use efficiency in BT cotton vis-à-vis Non BT cotton cultivation and (ii) To decompose the influence of factors and BT technology on output change.

Study Area and Sampling Procedure

The study used Multi-stage stratified random sampling method to select the respondents from among the farm households. The study is based on sample survey of selected farm households in six villages of Warangal and Guntur districts of the Andhra Pradesh state in India. It was decided to select a sample of 408 farm households. Taking district as a unit, the sample size of farm households for a district was kept at 204. Thus in the sample there is one village each for the 12 Mandals in the two districts. After selecting villages, a census survey of farm households was conducted to prepare a comprehensive list of all farm households cultivating cotton in each village, irrespective of the extent of area cultivated and ownership of land. The size of the sample for each village was fixed in proportion to the percentage of the cotton farmers in that village. Once the sample size was fixed for the village, the sample size for each stratum was determined in a proportionate manner. From each stratum, sample respondents were selected by following the systematic sampling method, using a random start. A detailed structured questionnaire was used to elicit the information from the farm households. The data collection has done during December 2007 - January 2008.

Models and Methods

It can be observed from the earlier studies that introduction of technology triggered a process by which the land productivity is increased significantly. These are only preliminary inferences about the complex relationship between farm productivity and

technology. It is expected that the use of BT seeds will result in changes in the input pattern, which in turn effect land productivity. Thus it can be inferred that increase in land productivity under BT cotton cultivation is not only through the use of BT cotton seeds but also by the changes in the use of other factors in production. Therefore it is essential to decompose the total increase in production per acre into increase due to BT cotton seeds and increase due to the changes in the use of other inputs.

The total change in output per acre after the introduction of BT cotton has been calculated by comparing output in BT cotton and Non-BT cotton crop situations. From the analysis of previous studies it is assumed that production conditions of both BT cotton and Non BT cotton cultivation is characterized by constant returns to scale (Mahendra Dev S., et al, 2007). This may imply that scale effects are eliminated and farm level Cob Douglass Production function can be expressed in terms of an acre. Further, it is observed that use of BT cotton in the study area has brought about a structural change in general and the technological parameters of the production function with BT cotton cultivation are different from those of Non-BT cotton cultivation.

The efficiency of the technology can be measured in terms of productivity per unit of input used. It is expected that the use of BT seeds reduce the cost of pesticides and the cost of labour used to apply the pesticide, which in turn enable the farmers to intensify the use of other basic inputs. Thus the high intensity of appropriate mix of basic inputs rises output. The upward shift in the production functions makes it possible to obtain additional output per unit of land. With the same amount of other inputs or in other words with lesser amount of inputs, it becomes possible to get the same level of output per acre.

Production function modal

The Cob Douglass Production function expressed in per acre term for both BT cotton and Non BT cotton cultivation can be expressed in the following forms.

$$\ln Y_B = \ln A_B + \alpha_1 \ln X_{B1} + \alpha_2 \ln X_{B2} + \alpha_3 \ln X_{B3} + \alpha_4 \ln X_{B4} \quad (\text{Equation- 1})$$

$$\ln Y_{NB} = \ln A_{NB} + \beta_1 \ln X_{NB1} + \beta_2 \ln X_{NB2} + \beta_3 \ln X_{NB3} + \beta_4 \ln X_{NB4} \quad (\text{Equation- 2})$$

Y_B = Output per acre in BT cotton cultivation

Y_{NB} = Output per acre in Non-BT cotton cultivation

X_{B1} = Value of seed used per acre in BT cultivation

X_{B2} = Value of fertilizer used per acre in BT cultivation

X_{B3} = Value of pesticides used per acre in BT cultivation

X_{B4} = Value of Human labour per acre in BT cultivation

X_{NB1} = Value of seed used per acre in Non BT cultivation

X_{NB2} = Value of fertilizer used per acre in Non-BT cultivation

X_{NB3} = Value of pesticides used per acre in Non-BT cultivation

X_{NB4} = Value of human labour used per acre in Non-BT cultivation

$\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4$ are the output elasticity co-efficients of seeds, fertilizer, pesticides and human labour in BT cultivation where as $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ are the corresponding elasticity coefficient for the Non-BT cultivation.

Taking the difference between the equation-1 and equation-2 and adding some terms subtracting the same terms.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \ln Y_B - \ln Y_{NB} = (\ln A_B - \ln A_{NB}) \\
& + (\alpha_1 \ln X_{B1} - \beta_1 \ln X_{NB1} + \alpha_1 \ln X_{NB1} - \alpha_1 \ln X_{NB1}) \\
& + (\alpha_2 \ln X_{B2} - \beta_2 \ln X_{NB2} + \alpha_2 \ln X_{NB2} - \alpha_2 \ln X_{NB2}) \\
& + (\alpha_3 \ln X_{B3} - \beta_3 \ln X_{NB3} + \alpha_3 \ln X_{NB3} - \alpha_3 \ln X_{NB3}) \\
& + (\alpha_4 \ln X_{B4} - \beta_4 \ln X_{NB4} + \alpha_4 \ln X_{NB4} - \alpha_4 \ln X_{NB4})
\end{aligned} \tag{Equation- 3}$$

Rearranging the terms in equation-3

$$\begin{aligned}
& (\ln Y_B - \ln Y_{NB}) = (\ln A_B - \ln A_{NB}) \\
& + [(\alpha_1 - \beta_1) \ln X_{NB1} + (\alpha_2 - \beta_2) \ln X_{NB2} + (\alpha_3 - \beta_3) \ln X_{NB3} + (\alpha_4 - \beta_4) \ln X_{NB4}] + \\
& [\alpha_1 (\ln X_{NB1} - \ln X_{NB1}) + \alpha_2 (\ln X_{B2} - \ln X_{NB2}) + \alpha_3 (\ln X_{B3} - \ln X_{NB3}) + \alpha_4 (\ln X_{B4} - \ln X_{NB4})]
\end{aligned} \tag{Equation- 4}$$

Decomposition Model

The following log linear estimable forms of equations were used for examining the structural break in production relation (Bisaliah, 1977).

$$\begin{aligned}
\ln [Y_B / Y_{NB}] &= [\ln (A_M / A_N)] + \\
& [(\alpha_1 - \beta_1) \ln X_{NB1} + (\alpha_2 - \beta_2) \ln X_{NB2} + (\alpha_3 - \beta_3) \ln X_{NB3} + (\alpha_4 - \beta_4) \ln X_{NB4}] + \\
& [(\alpha_1 \ln (X_{B1} / X_{NB1}) + \alpha_2 \ln (X_{B2} / X_{NB2}) + \alpha_3 \ln (X_{B1} / X_{NB3}) + \alpha_4 \ln (X_{B4} / X_{NB4}))]
\end{aligned} \tag{Equation- 5}$$

The above equation permits us to decompose the total difference in output per acre in between BT cotton cultivation and Non BT cotton cultivation into BT technology component and other input components. It decomposes the natural logarithm of the ratio of per acre output in Non-BT cotton cultivation, which is approximately an aggregate per cent change in output per acre with the introduction of Biotechnology.

The impact of Biotechnology can be observed by looking at the changes in intercept term and slope parameters. The first two bracketed expressions in equation-5 measures the changes in output per acre due to change in the intercept term and change in the slope parameters as a result of use of BT cotton seed. The second bracketed expression, sum of arithmetic change in output elasticities weighed by the logarithm of value of that input used, is a measure of change in output due to shift in slope parameters of the production function.

The third bracketed expression is the sum of logarithms of the ratios for each input of BT cotton cultivation to Non-BT cotton cultivation, each weighed by the output elasticity of that input. This expression is a measure of change in output due to difference in the per acre values of seed fertilizers, pesticides, and human labour input used and the given output elasticity of these inputs under BT cotton production technology. The estimated values of least square regression coefficient elasticities for BT cotton and Non-BT cotton cultivation is presented in table-1

Table1: Per acre OLS estimates of the Production function.

Variable	Parameter	Estimated value	t- value	R ²
BT cotton				
Constant	Log A _B	10.97	11.89	0.78
Seed	α_1	0.186*	5.76	
Fertilizer	α_2	0.271*	9.38	
Pesticide	α_3	0.076	0.87	
Human Labour	α_4	0.487**	2.33	
Non-BT cotton				
Constant	Log A _{NB}	8.76	13.33	0.82
Seed	β_1	0.165	2.68	
Fertilizer	β_2	0.261*	6.33	
Pesticide	β_3	0.116*	3.05	
Human Labour	β_4	0.461**	2.93	

Note: The dependent variable is the value of output (in Rs.) per acre.

*Significant at one per cent level

**Significant at five per cent level

Results and Discussions

Resource Use Efficiency

The estimated production function appears to be best fit as the variation explained in yield by different farm inputs varies between 0.78 and 1.82 per cent in BT and Non-BT cotton crop situations. It is further observed that most of the elasticity coefficients of inputs have registered the expected signs with a prior economic logic and found to be significant at probability levels ranging from 5 to 10 per cent.

The results of the estimated production functions reveal that fertilizer is the most important input to which output is highly responsive in both BT and Non-BT cotton crop situations. The elasticity of output with respect to fertilizer is found to be positive and significant at 5 per cent probability level in both BT and Non-BT crop situations. From the analysis of the results it is found that expenditure on seeds is another important input to which output is highly responsive in both cotton crop situations.

The coefficients associated with expenditure on seed is found to be positive and significant at 5 per cent probability level of significance in both categories of farms. On the other hand it is observed that elasticity coefficient of output with respect to pesticides is higher in Non BT cotton cultivation as compared to BT cotton cultivation. That is, output elasticity of pesticide is higher in Non BT cotton

cultivation than that of in BT cotton cultivation, which reveals that an increase in expenditure on pesticides resulted in increased output in Non- BT cotton cultivation when compared to BT cotton cultivation. The elasticity coefficient of pesticides though found to be positive in BT cotton cultivation, it is not significant. The elasticity coefficient of pesticides is found to be positive and significant in Non BT cotton crop situation.

It could be observed that the elasticity coefficient with respect to human labour is positive and significant in both BT cotton and Non-BT cotton crop situations. Farther it is observed that output elasticity of human labour is found to be higher in BT cotton cultivation when compared to Non- BT cotton crop situation.

The elasticity coefficient with respect to human labour is positive and significant in both BT cotton and Non-BT cotton crop situations. The output elasticity of human labour is higher in BT cotton cultivation when compared to Non- BT cotton crop situation.

Decomposition analysis

In order to evaluate the net impact of BT technology and other inputs on cotton productivity, the results of the decomposition analysis is presented in table-2. The percentage change in value of output has been decomposed into percentage change in output due to BT technology and per cent change in output due to change in per acre use of other inputs. The total estimated change in the value output with an access to use of BT cotton seed worked out to 26.56 per cent, which is marginally higher than observed change in output. The difference between the observed and estimated changes in output in both the forms may be because of the non inclusion of certain factors, either due to the problem of quantification or due to non- availability of data.

The net impact of BT technology in cotton crop can be captured by adding the first two bracketed expressions of equation-2. BT technology alone is estimated to have increased the output by 10.88 per cent. This could reveal that with some level of use of seeds, fertilizers, pesticides and human labour, the farmers have obtained 10.88 per cent more output per acre by using BT cotton seeds when compared to those who have used Non-BT cotton seeds. The differences in the use of seed, fertilizer, pesticide and human labour have increased the output per acre by 8.15, 0.61, 1.68 and 5.21 per cent respectively. Changes in the use of all these inputs put together have been increased by about 15.65 per cent.

Table2: Decomposition analysis of total difference in output (Value in Rs.) per acre between BT cotton and Non- BT cotton cultivation.

	Item	Percentage attributable
	Total observe difference in output	24.50
1.	BT technology	10.88
2.	Changes in inputs	
a)	Seed	8.15

b)	Fertilizer	0.61
c)	Pesticide	1.68
d)	Human Labour	5.21
	All inputs	15.65
	Total estimated change due to all sources	26.53

Conclusion

The study revealed that the productivity difference between BT and Non BT cotton farmers was largely attributable to BT technology. The results of the estimated production functions reveal that seeds and fertilizer is the most important input to which output is highly responsive in both BT and Non-BT cotton crop situations. On the other hand, it is observed that elasticity co-efficient of output with respect to pesticides is higher in Non BT cotton cultivation as compared to BT cotton cultivation. The output elasticity of pesticide is higher in Non BT cotton cultivation than that of in BT cotton cultivation. An increase in expenditure on pesticides resulted in increased output in Non BT cotton cultivation when compared to BT cotton cultivation. Further, the plant protection chemicals and other inputs were used optimally by BT cotton farmers as against excessive use by Non BT cotton farmers. Therefore, it is necessary to motivate the farmers for cultivation of BT cotton with appropriate extension strategies and policy measures. The elasticity coefficient with respect to human labour is positive and significant in both BT cotton and Non-BT cotton crop situations. The output elasticity of human labour is higher in BT cotton cultivation when compared to Non- BT cotton crop situation. The results of the decomposition revealed that the net impact of BT technology alone is estimated to have increased the output by 10.88 per cent. That is with some level of use of seeds, fertilizers, pesticides and human labour, the farmers have obtained 10.88 per cent more output per acre by using BT cotton seeds when compared to those who have used Non-BT cotton seeds. Changes in the use of all other inputs put together have been increased output by about 15.65 per cent. Therefore, BT cotton needs to be expanded among all cotton growers to harvest the benefits in terms of higher yield and income.

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